

MURAKKAB ELEKTR ENERGETIKA TIZIMLARIDA KICHIK TEBRANISHLARNI TAHLIL ETISH

Toxir MAXMUDOV

Islom Karimov nomidagi
Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
dotsenti

Annotatsiya. Maqolada statik turg'unlikni tadqiq etishni amalga oshirish imkonini beruvchi ko'p mashinali elektr energetika tizimining matematik modeli ishlab chiqilgan. Uch generatorli rostlanadigan elektr tizimining statik turg'unligini hisob-kitobi amalga oshirildi. Natijada, o'rganilayotgan tizimning xarakteristik tenglamasi ildizlarining qiymatlari hisoblab chiqildi. Olingan natijalar klassik tadqiqotlar natijalari bilan sifat jihatidan mos keladi, bu taklif qilingan modelning adekvatligi va real tizimda sodir bo'layotgan dinamik jarayonlarning to'g'ri aks ettirilishi natijasidir.

Kalit so'zlar: elektr energetika tizimi, o'tkinchi jarayonlar, qo'zg'atishni avtomatik rostlagich, matritsa spektri, rejim parametrlari.

АНАЛИЗ МАЛЫХ КОЛЕБАНИЙ В СЛОЖНЫХ ЭЛЕКТРОЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИХ СИСТЕМАХ

Тоxир МАХМУДОВ,

Доцент Ташкентского государственного
технического университета имени
Ислама Каримова

Аннотация. В статье разработана математическая модель многомашинной электроэнергетической системы, позволяющая проводить исследования статической устойчивости. Проведен расчет статической устойчивости регулируемой трехгенераторной энергосистемы. В результате были рассчитаны значения корней характеристического уравнения исследуемой системы. Полученные результаты качественно согласуются с результатами классических исследований, что является следствием адекватности предложенной модели и правильного отражения динамических процессов, происходящих в реальной системе.

Ключевые слова: электроэнергетическая система, переходные процессы, автоматический регулятор возбуждения, матричный спектр, параметры режима.

ANALYSIS OF SMALL OSCILLATIONS IN COMPLEX ELECTRIC POWER SYSTEMS

Tokhir MAKHMUDOV,

Associate Professor of the
Tashkent State Technical University
named after Islam Karimov

Annotation. The article develops a mathematical model of a multi-machine electric power system, allowing to conduct studies of static stability. The calculation of static stability of a regulated three-generator power system is carried out. As a result, the values of the roots of the characteristic equation of the system under study were calculated. The obtained results are in qualitative agreement with the results of classical studies, which is a consequence of the adequacy of the proposed model and the correct reflection of the dynamic processes occurring in the real system.

Keywords: electric power system, transient processes, automatic excitation controller, matrix spectrum, mode parameters.

Kirish. Zamonaviy elektr tizimlarining ortib borayotgan murakkabligi, ularning tarkibiga raqamli va mantiqiy boshqaruv qurilmalarining kiritilishi elektr tizimlarining rejimlarini aniq va chuqur o'rganishni talab qiladi. Ushbu muammoni matritsali usullar yordamida muvaffaqiyatli hal qilish mumkin. Maqolada generatorlarning absolyut burchaklari asosida elektr tizimining

matritsa modeli taklif etilgan bo'lib, bu muammoning dolzarbligini va uni hal qilish usulini ta'kidlaydi.

Murakkab elektr tizimidagi o'tkinchi jarayonlarning matematik modeli.

Ushbu model elektr energetika tizimining (EET) i-chi agregatining validagi momentlar (kuchlar) muvozanatini hisobga olgan holda elektr tizimidagi o'tkinchi jarayonni tavsiflaydi va quyidagi shaklga ega [1]:

$$\frac{d^2 \delta_i}{dt^2} = \frac{\omega_0}{T_{ji}} [P_{\dot{\alpha}} - P_{Gi}], \quad (1)$$

bu yerda ω_0 – sinxron burchak chastotasi; T_{ji} , δ_i , P_{Ti} , P_{Gi} – mos ravishda i-chi agregatning inersiya doimiysi, i-chi generatorning yuklanish burchagi, i-chi turbinaning mexanik quvati, i-chi sinxron generatorning elektromagnit quvati.

Pozitsion idealizatsiyadagi i-chi sinxron generatorning elektromagnit quvvat tenglamasi quyidagi ko'rinishga ega [2]:

$$P_{Gi} = E_i^2 y_{ii} \sin \alpha_{ii} + \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n E_i E_j y_{ij} \sin(\delta_{ij} - \alpha_{ij}), \quad (2)$$

bu yerda E_i , E_j – i-chi va j-chi sinxron generatorlarning elektr yurutuvchi kuchi (e.yu.k); y_{ii} , y_{ij} – tarmoqning ichki va o'zaro o'tkazuvchanliklari; α_{ii} , α_{ij} – qo'shimcha burchaklar.

(2) chi tenglama nochiziqli hisoblanadi, chunki tenglamaning tashkil etuvchilari sinusoidal funksiya shaklida transsendent. Shuning uchun, EETning kichik tebranishlarini o'rganishda Teylor qatoriga yoyishi va ba'zi trigonometrik ifodalar qo'llaniladi, bu P_0 rejimining boshlang'ich nuqtasida (2) birlikning chiziqli bo'lmagan differensial tenglamasini chiziqshtirishga imkon beradi (P-rejim parametri: quvvat, kuchlanish va boshqalar), bu elektr tizimining statik turg'unligini o'rganishni soddalashtiradi. Bu holatda qo'llaniladigan kichik tebranishlar usuli, elektr tizimidagi kichik turtkilar bilan $P=P_0 \pm \Delta P$ og'ishlarni qabul qiladigan ish parametrlari kichik qiymatlarga o'zgarishi haqidagi farazga asoslanadi [3].

Transsendent funktsiyalar har qanday i va j uchun quyidagi ifodalar yordamida chiziqshtiriladi [4]:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{ij} &= \delta_i - \delta_j, \quad \delta_i = \delta_{i0} + \Delta \delta_i, \quad \delta_j = \delta_{j0} + \Delta \delta_j, \\ \delta_{ij} &= -\delta_{ij}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

va undan keyin

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sin(\delta_{ij} - \alpha_{ij}) &= \sin[(\delta_{i0} + \Delta\delta_i) - (\delta_{j0} + \Delta\delta_j) - \alpha_{ij}] = \\
 &= \sin[(\Delta\delta_i - \Delta\delta_j) + (\delta_{i0} - \delta_{j0} - \alpha_{ij})] = \\
 &= \Delta\delta_i \cos \beta_{ij} - \Delta\delta_j \cos \beta_{ij} + \sin \beta_{ij},
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

bu yerda $\beta_{ij} = \delta_{i0} - \delta_{j0} - \alpha_{ij}$.

Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, (4) tenglamasini olishda aniq ifodalar ishlatilgan:

$$\sin(\Delta\delta_i - \Delta\delta_j) \cong (\Delta\delta_i - \Delta\delta_j) \text{ \& } \cos(\Delta\delta_i - \Delta\delta_j) \cong 1,$$

generator yuklama burchaklarining kichik og'ishlari uchun amal qiladi.

(3), (4) ni hisobga olgan holda (2) o'zgarishlardan so'ng (1) tenglama quyidagi shaklni oladi:

$$\frac{d^2\delta_i}{dt^2} = \frac{\omega_0}{T_{ji}} [P_{Ti} - (E_i^2 y_{ii} \sin \alpha_{ii} - \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n b_{ij} \Delta\delta_j + b_{ii} \Delta\delta_i + c_{ij})], \tag{5}$$

va boshlang'ich rejim parametrlarini va nisbatni hisobga olgan holda, natijada, og'ishlarda differensial tenglamaga olib keladi [5]:

$$\frac{d^2\Delta\delta_i}{dt^2} = \frac{\omega_0}{T_{ji}} [\sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n b_{ij} \Delta\delta_j - b_{ii} \Delta\delta_i], \tag{6}$$

$$b_{ij} = a_{ij} \cos \beta_{ij}, \quad a_{ij} = E_i E_j y_{ij}, \quad b_{ii} = \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n b_{ij}, \quad c_{ij} = \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n a_{ij} \sin \beta_{ij},$$

$$\text{bu yerda } P_{Ti} - (E_i^2 y_{ii} \sin \alpha_{ii} + c_{ij}) = 0.$$

i-sinxron generator rotorining dempfer berklarini hisobga olgan holda, (6) chi tenglama quyidagi shaklni oladi:

$$\frac{d^2\delta_i}{dt^2} = \frac{\omega_0}{T_{ji}} [\sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n b_{ij} \Delta\delta_j - b_{ii} \Delta\delta_i - P_{di} \frac{d\Delta\delta_i}{dt}], \tag{7}$$

bu yerda P_{di} – i-generatorning umumlashtirilgan dempfer momentining koeffitsiyenti.

E.yu.k ning og'ishini hisobga olgan holda, i-sinxron generatorning (7) tenglamasi shaklini oladi [6]:

$$\frac{d^2\delta_i}{dt^2} = \frac{\omega_0}{T_{ji}} [\sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n b_{ij} \Delta\delta_j - b_{ii} \Delta\delta_i - P_{di} \frac{d\Delta\delta_i}{dt} - \frac{dP_i}{dE_{qi}} \Delta E_{qi}]. \tag{8}$$

(8)chi tenglamaning o'ziga xos xususiyati shundaki, u tizim generatorlarining

nisbiy burchaklariga nisbatan hisob qilinadi va, masalan, uch generatorli elektr tizimi uchun quyidagi shaklga ega [7]:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2\Delta\delta_1}{dt^2} &= \frac{\omega_0}{T_{j1}}[-b_{11}\Delta\delta_1 + b_{12}\Delta\delta_2 + b_{13}\Delta\delta_3 - P_{d1}\frac{d\Delta\delta_1}{dt} - \frac{dP_1}{dE_{q1}}\Delta E_{q1}], \\ \frac{d^2\Delta\delta_2}{dt^2} &= \frac{\omega_0}{T_{j2}}[b_{21}\Delta\delta_1 - b_{22}\Delta\delta_2 + b_{23}\Delta\delta_3 - P_{d2}\frac{d\Delta\delta_2}{dt} - \frac{dP_2}{dE_{q2}}\Delta E_{q2}], \\ \frac{d^2\Delta\delta_3}{dt^2} &= \frac{\omega_0}{T_{j3}}[b_{31}\Delta\delta_1 + b_{32}\Delta\delta_2 - b_{33}\Delta\delta_3 - P_{d3}\frac{d\Delta\delta_3}{dt} - \frac{dP_3}{dE_{q3}}\Delta E_{q3}]. \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Og'ishlardagi i-sinxron mashinaning qo'zg'atish zanjirida elektromagnit o'tkinchi jarayonlarning tenglamalari quyidagi ko'rinishga ega [8-10]:

$$T_{di}' \frac{d\Delta E_{qi}}{dt} = \Delta E_{qi} - \Delta E_{qei}, \tag{10}$$

$$T_{ei} \frac{d\Delta E_{qei}}{dt} = \Delta U_{QARi} - \Delta E_{qei}, \tag{11}$$

$$T_{pi} \frac{d\Delta U_{QARi}}{dt} = \Delta e_i - \Delta U_{QARi}, \tag{12}$$

bu yerda T_{di}' , T_{ei} , T_{pi} - mos ravishda qo'zg'atish cho'lg'amining o'tkinchi vaqt doimiysi, qo'zg'atgichning vaqt doimiysi, avtomatik qo'zg'atish rostlagich (QAR) vaqt doimiysi;

ΔE_{qi} , ΔE_{qei} , ΔU_{QARi} - sinxron, majburiy e.y.u.k. ning og'ishlari. va mos ravishda avtomatik qo'zg'atish rostlagichining chiqishidagi kuchlanish. QAR kanallari orqali Δe_i signallarining ideallashtirilgan shaklda shakllanishi (agar QAR ning differensial elementlarining doimiy vaqtlari nolga teng deb hisoblansa) quyidagicha ifodalanishi mumkin [11]:

$$\Delta e = \sum_1^k \left(k_{0Pk} \Delta P_k + k_{1Pk} \left(\frac{d\Delta P_k}{dt} \right) + k_{2Pk} \left(\frac{d^2\Delta P_k}{dt^2} \right) \right), \tag{13}$$

bu yerda k_{0Pk} , k_{1Pk} , k_{2Pk} - og'ish kanallari uchun QAR kuchaytirish koeffitsiyentlari, rejim parametrlarining birinchi va ikkinchi hosilalari ΔP_k , mos ravishda, k - sozlanish rejim parametrlari soni.

(7) va (8) tenglamalarning afzalligi ularning nisbiy burchaklariga ($\Delta\delta_{ij}$) emas, balki generatorlarning absolyut yuklama burchaklarining ($\Delta\delta_i$) og'ishlariga bog'liqligidir, bu esa hisoblash qulayligini ta'minlaydi, chunki bu tenglamalar tugun kuchlanish tenglamalari bilan birlashtirilishi mumkin va ularning yechimlari absolyut burchaklarning qiymatlarini beradi [12].

Rejim parametrlarining kichik turtkilariga tegishli (1)-(13) o'zgartirishlaridan so'ng kuch ta'sirli QAR ga ega bo'lgan n ta generatorli elektr tizimining dinamikasi uchun o'lchamdagi (4nx4n) umumlashtirilgan A_{Σ} blokli matritsasini olish mumkin [1]:

$$A_{\Sigma} = \begin{bmatrix} 0_{n \times n} & I_{n \times n} & 0_{n \times n} & 0_{n \times n} \\ A_{21(n \times n)} & A_{22(n \times n)} & A_{23(n \times n)} & 0_{n \times n} \\ 0_{n \times n} & 0_{n \times n} & A_{33(n \times n)} & A_{34(n \times n)} \\ A_{41(n \times n)} & A_{42(n \times n)} & 0_{n \times n} & A_{42(n \times n)} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

A_{Σ} matritsasining tashkil etuvchilari [2] da aniqlangan. Bunday holda, elektr tizimi rejimining parametrlarini o'z ichiga olgan rejim parametrlarining ustun vektori quyidagi shaklga ega:

$$x = [\Delta\delta_1 \dots \Delta\delta_n \ ; \ \Delta\dot{\delta}_1 \dots \Delta\dot{\delta}_n \ ; \ \Delta\dot{E}_{q1} \dots \Delta\dot{E}_{qn} \ ; \ \Delta\dot{E}_{qe1} \dots \Delta\dot{E}_{qen}]^T. \quad (15)$$

Masalan, uch generatorli EET uchun (1-rasm), kuch ta'sirli QAR kuchlanish va generatorlarning yuklama burchagi ($\Delta\delta_i, \Delta U_{\Gamma i}$), shuningdek, ularning birinchi hosilalari ($\Delta\dot{\delta}_i, \Delta\dot{U}$) dagi og'ishlarga reaksiya beradi degan farazda

1-rasm. Uch generatorli elektr tizimining sxemasi.

i-chi generator uchun QARning tenglamasi quyidagi shaklga ega:

$$\Delta U_{QARi} = k_{0\delta} \Delta\delta_i + k_{1\delta} \frac{d\Delta\delta_i}{dt} + k_{0UGi} \Delta U_{Gi} + k_{1UGi} \frac{d\Delta U_{Gi}}{dt}, \quad (16)$$

bu yerda $i=1 \div 3$, va avtomatik rostlagichning vaqt doimiysi hisobga olinmaydi ($T_{pi}=0$). Bunday holda, A_{Σ} matritsasi quyidagi ko'rinishni oladi [2]:

$$A_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \hline -a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{dP_1}{dE_{q1}} \frac{\omega_0}{T_{j1}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{21} & -a_{22} & a_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{dP_2}{dE_{q2}} \frac{\omega_0}{T_{j2}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & -a_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{dP_3}{dE_{q3}} \frac{\omega_0}{T_{j3}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \hline 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{T_{e1}} & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{T_{e1}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{T_{e2}} & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{T_{e2}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{T_{e3}} & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{T_{e3}} \\ \hline \frac{k_{0\delta 1}}{T_{e1}} & 0 & 0 & \frac{k_{1\delta 1}}{T_{e1}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{T_{e1}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{k_{0\delta 2}}{T_{e2}} & 0 & 0 & \frac{k_{1\delta 2}}{T_{e2}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{T_{e2}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{k_{0\delta 3}}{T_{e3}} & 0 & 0 & \frac{k_{1\delta 3}}{T_{e3}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{T_{e3}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

EET rejimi parametrlarining holat fazosining ustun vektori:

$$x = [\Delta\delta_1 \ \Delta\delta_2 \ \Delta\delta_3 \ \Delta\dot{\delta}_1 \ \Delta\dot{\delta}_2 \ \Delta\dot{\delta}_3 \ \Delta\dot{E}_{q1} \ \Delta\dot{E}_{q2} \ \Delta\dot{E}_{q3} \ \Delta\dot{E}_{qe1} \ \Delta\dot{E}_{qe2} \ \Delta\dot{E}_{qe3}]^T.$$

Ko'rib turganimizdek, 3 ta generatordan iborat elektr tizimi dinamikasining umumlashtirilgan A_3 matritsasi tizim rejimi va mashina qo'zg'atishini avtomatik roslash parametrlaridan hosil bo'ladi, shuning uchun u ushbu EETdagi o'tkinchi jarayonlarni to'liq tavsiflaydi. A_3 matritsasi kam to'ldirilgan bo'lib, bu n ta generatorni o'z ichiga olgan murakkab tizim uchun ham xosdir, shuning uchun bu fakt EETning hisoblash va eksperimental tadqiqotlarida taklif qilingan matematik modelning hisoblash afzalliklarini aniqlaydi.

Misol. Misol tariqasida, birinchi generatorning QAR kuchaytirish koeffitsiyentlari $k_{0\delta 1}=18.75$, $k_{1\delta 1}=3.75$, vaqt doimiysi $T_{e1}=0,5$ s bo'lgan uch generatorli elektr tizimining dinamikasi matritsasi (17) A_3 ni ko'rib chiqaylik va qolgan generatorlarning QAR kanallari uzilgan deb hisoblaymiz. Hisoblash natijasi quyida ko'rsatilgan.

$$A_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -235.3565 & 155.8297 & 99.8200 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.4167 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 104.5232 & -120.3483 & 51.6890 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.5214 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 50.6447 & 39.2440 & -94.1103 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.5844 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.25 & 0 & 0 & -1.25 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.4286 & 0 & 0 & -1.4286 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.6667 & 0 & 0 & -1.6667 \\ 20 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -2.5 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -2.2222 \end{bmatrix}$$

Tanlangan rejim va tizim parametrlari bilan uch generatorli EET A_3 o'z dinamikasi matritsasining spektri: $-0,0012 \pm 17,9944i$; $-0,0001 \pm 11,9462i$; 4.1082 ; $-4,0995$; $-1,9571$; 1.2009 ; $1,4286$; $1,6667$; $-2,5$; -2.2222 ga teng va uning 3D vizualizatsiyasi 2-rasmda ko'rsatilgan. Elektr tizimi noturg'un. Generatorlarning burchagi va kuchlanishining og'ishi va birinchi hosilasi asosida qolgan generatorlarning QAR tizimlarini kiritish o'rganilayotgan tizimning turg'unligini ta'minlashi mumkin.

2-rasm. A_3 Gurovits matritsasi bilan uch generatorli elektr tizimi spektrining 3D vizualizatsiyasi.

Xulosa. Murakkab elektr tizimlarining dinamik xususiyatlari oddiy EET xususiyatlaridan sezilarli darajada farq qilishi mumkin, bu ko'plab to'liq miqyosli va namunaviy tajribalar, hisoblash va eksperimental tadqiqotlar bilan tasdiqlangan [3, 4]. Ko'p mashinali elektr tizimida boshqaruv moslamalarining parametrlarini tanlash eng oddiy EETga qaraganda ancha murakkab. Shuning uchun, qoida tariqasida, ko'p mashinali EET holatida bitta generator yoki bitta stansiya sozlanishi hisoblanadi va ularning QAR parametrlari belgilangan vazifa asosida aniqlanadi – tebranishlarni so'ndirish, zarur turg'unlik zaxirasini ta'minlash, va boshqa stansiyalar generatorlarining QAR parametrlari butun tizimning turg'unligini ta'minlash va rejim parametrlarining mumkin bo'lgan tebranishlarini kamaytirish zaruratidan kelib chiqqan holda tanlanadi. Shuning uchun boshqa generatorlarning QAR ni joriy qilish keyingi tadqiqotlar mavzusi bo'lgan nazorat parametrlarini (sintez) tanlash bo'yicha qo'shimcha tadqiqotlarni talab qiladi.

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